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DISTANCE EDUCATION IN UKRAINIAN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS, ITS PROBLEMS AND PROSPECTS FOR THE FUTURE

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Distance education is one of the most promising trends in the development of modern education. Distance education meets all the requirements of the information society, namely: mass education for all population categories regardless of their place of residence; open, person-oriented and lifelong learning.

Distance education in Ukraine has existed for more than twenty years. The state policy in the field of distance education determines the concept developed in 2000 for distance education development. According to the policy, distance education is a form of education that is equivalent to full-time, evening, part-time and external education, implemented through distance learning technologies. In addition, the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine number 1494 dated September 23, 2003, approved the "Program for the Development of the Distance Learning System for 2004-2006". The adoption of the new "Regulations on Distance Learning" as revised in 2015 and the recognition of distance education in the new wording of the Law "On Higher Education" as revised in 2018 are important for the distance learning development in Ukraine. Distance learning refers to the individualized process of acquiring knowledge, skills and methods of a person's cognitive activity, which occurs mainly through the distant participants' indirect interaction in the educational process in a specialized environment, which functions based on modern psychological, pedagogical, information and communication technologies.

Currently, Ukraine has no single focal point for the development and implementation of state policy in the field of distance education development. There has been an ambiguous idea of distance learning in Ukraine for many years. The reasons for this are different approaches to its organization at educational institutions, the lack of a common concept and standards.

The Paris Communiqué, held in 2018 concerning the further introduction of the European Higher Education Area, states that higher education institutions should prepare their students and help their teachers act creatively in a digitalized environment, and make better use of digital and blended education with appropriate quality assurance in order to enhance lifelong and flexible learning, foster digital skills and competences, improve data analysis, educational research, and foresight, and remove regulatory barriers to open and digital education provision.

Distance learning technologies are used at most higher education institutions of Ukraine, but the necessity of the introduction and development of remote technology is questionable both to faculties and students.

Many official documents have been adopted in Ukraine, which fully ensure the implementation of distance learning in the country, the organization of qualitative training of specialists of various qualification fields. However, teachers distinguish such obstacles for the development of distance education as their lack of

desire and material interest, lack of computer skills, inadequate computer literacy, and their biased attitude towards innovative technologies.

Most of the teachers at higher education institutions remain followers of blended learning, which effectively combines traditional and distance learning technologies, but not full-fledged distance education. At the same time, they are trying to modernize the national education system according to modern standards and needs of integration into the world educational space and continue to introduce modern technologies of distance learning. Therefore, a promising trend in the development of distance learning at Ukrainian higher education institutions is the close collaboration of developers of software products for distance learning, distance education methodologists, and professors of higher education institutions for the strategy development of the new information technology application in distance learning.

Higher education institutions of Ukraine independently organize distance learning with the involvement of state and sponsorship funds, grants, student fees, which adversely affects the pace of distance learning implementation. The collaboration of higher education institutions with commercial structures in the field of corporate learning is another promising trend in the development of distance education in Ukraine. Such cooperation will allow higher education institutions to obtain additional sources of funding, including those for the organization of effective training.

Higher education institutions pay much attention to the support of distance education: separate specialized distance learning subdivisions have been created, there are individuals who are responsible for the informational support of distance education, distance learning training courses for teachers and students have been organized. However, the peopleware indicator for distance learning remains extremely low. In addition, the data indicate the significant unevenness of this peopleware: from the total absence of trained specialists for the distance learning organization to a maximum of 320 people, however, this maximum is provided by only 23 teachers per 1000 students. Therefore, one of the promising trends of distance learning development in Ukraine is the training of specialists in the field of distance education.

The high complexity of the development of distance learning courses complicates the work of teachers and technical staff. The creation of high-quality educational content, interactive multimedia interaction, qualitative multi-level tests takes a lot of time. Therefore, for the development of distance learning, it is essential not only to train specialists how to use remote learning technologies but also how to develop platforms with intuitive, non-complex software interfaces for creating distance courses, to promote the distribution of qualitative software for the distance learning organization.

For the past 10 years, massive open distance courses have become widespread. In Ukraine, such courses have been organized by M. Ye. Zhukovskiy National Aerospace University "Kharkiv Aviation Institute", the Problem Laboratory of Distance Learning at the National Technical University of Ukraine "Kharkiv Polytechnic Institute", Taras Shevchenko Kyiv National University, and Luhansk State Institute of Culture and Arts.

The development of the Internet of things, virtual and augmented reality, the proliferation of the artificial intelligence systems and the management systems of the next generation education, the creation of natural user interfaces encourage the teacher comprehension and elaboration of methods of their application in the distance education. It is necessary to develop information resources, educational and methodological developments to support new technologies of distance learning at higher education institutions of Ukraine. This is another promising direction in the development of distance education in Ukraine.

Distance education in M. Ye. Zhukovskiy National Aerospace University "Kharkiv Aviation Institute" has become more common in recent years than it was before. Most of the teachers passed the distance education training course in 2019. They have learned how to work and create a learning environment on the university distance education website. The teachers from the Software Engineering and Business faculty have created this website and instruments to help facilitate teachers' and students' work. But, before this work is facilitated, a lot of work has to be done to provide students and colleagues with all the content needed for a productive teaching-learning process. Nevertheless, this website is very useful and it gives all the opportunities for fruitful cooperation between teachers and their colleagues, teachers and students. All the necessary information is kept there and it is very convenient, especially, when there are such unpredicted situations as isolation period or quarantine. During such periods distance education becomes an essential form of education. At other better periods, distance learning can be combined with traditional education (blended learning). The benefits of blended learning are giving all the necessary knowledge to the students with the opportunity of having access to the World Wide Web. Distance education also becomes indispensable when students or teachers have no opportunity to come to the room of their interlocutors. This problem can be solved by having stable access to the Internet and skills of working with the computer and with the distance education website. Apart from websites, many other programs help to provide continuous distance education, such as Skype, Google meet, Discord, Zoom, Viber, Telegram, E-mail, etc. for web conferences and for exchanging the written information. The distance education website of M. Ye. Zhukovskiy National Aerospace University "Kharkiv Aviation Institute" combines all the benefits of these programs and provided its resources and activities for successful work. It is only necessary to be able to work with all these resources and activities to obtain desired results. Currently, a lot of new courses for different learning purposes are being developed and improved. All the teachers of M. Ye. Zhukovskiy National Aerospace University "Kharkiv Aviation Institute" constantly work on the improvement of courses' content in order to achieve ideal learning provision.

To sum it up, despite all the existing problems with distance education in Ukrainian higher education institutions, there are so many prospects of distance learning development and it depends only on us what distance education we will have in the future.